

IDENTITY AS A LEGAL CONCEPT & ECONOMIC IDENTITY

Parama Chakraborty¹

B.A in English language and literature

M.A in English language and literature

¹*Eden Mohila College, Dhaka University, Bangladesh.*

Corresponding Author's Email: paramachakraborty335@gmail.com

Abstract

Identity is a multifaceted concept with various meanings and interpretations. In a legal context, identity refers to the characteristics and attributes that define an individual or entity, which are recognized and regulated by law. Identity is a crucial legal concept because it determines an individual's rights, privileges, and obligations under the law. Legal identity is created through the process of identification, which involves providing evidence of one's personal attributes, such as name, age, and nationality, to establish legal recognition. Identity documents, such as passports and birth certificates, are essential tools for establishing legal identity, and their issuance and recognition are regulated by national and international legal frameworks. Legal identity is fundamental to access essential services, such as healthcare, education, and financial services. It is also necessary for exercising civil and political rights, such as voting and freedom of movement. Therefore, ensuring universal legal identity is critical for promoting inclusivity and reducing social and economic inequality.

Keywords: Advancement of technology, Identification, Personal data, Verification, Socio-economic.

Introduction

Identity is a multifaceted concept that has been widely explored in various fields, including psychology, sociology, and philosophy. In a legal context, identity refers to the characteristics and attributes that define an individual or entity, which are recognized and regulated by law. Legal identity is created through the process of identification, which involves providing evidence of one's personal attributes, such as name, age, and nationality, to establish legal recognition. The concept of legal identity is crucial because it determines an individual's rights, privileges, and obligations under the law.

The process of identification involves collecting and verifying personal data to establish legal identity. The collection of personal data may include biographical information, such as name, date of birth, and place of birth, as well as biometric data, such as fingerprints or facial recognition.

The verification process may involve comparing the collected data against a central database, such as a national registry, to establish the individual's identity. Once the individual's identity is established, they may be issued an identity document, such as a passport or a national ID card, which serves as proof of their legal identity.

Legal identity is essential for accessing essential services, such as healthcare, education, and financial services. It is also necessary for exercising civil and political rights, such as voting and freedom of movement. Without legal identity, individuals may be excluded from these essential services and may be unable to exercise their rights, leading to social and economic inequality. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) recognize the importance of legal identity for achieving inclusive and sustainable development, and SDG 16.9 aims to provide legal identity for all, including birth registration, by 2030.

The regulation of legal identity is governed by national and international legal frameworks. National legal frameworks may differ from country to country, but they typically establish the requirements for identification and the issuance of identity documents. International legal frameworks, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Convention on the Rights of the Child, recognize the importance of legal identity and establish standards for ensuring universal legal identity.

Despite the recognized importance of legal identity, there are still challenges in ensuring universal legal identity. One significant challenge is the lack of birth registration, which is the first step in establishing legal identity. According to the UNDP, around one-third of children worldwide are not registered at birth, I means they may be unable to access essential services or exercise their rights later in life. Other challenges include the cost and accessibility of identity documents, particularly for marginalized communities, and the lack of a harmonized legal framework for cross-border identification.

The implications of legal identity on society are significant. Ensuring universal legal identity is critical for promoting inclusivity and reducing social and economic inequality. It also has implications for national security and the prevention of identity theft and fraud. The role of legal identity in society is complex and multifaceted, and it requires ongoing attention and regulation to ensure that all individuals have equal access to essential services and can exercise their rights.

The Process of Identification: Establishing Legal Identity

Legal identity is a crucial legal concept that determines an individual's rights, privileges, and obligations under the law. The process of identification and the issuance and recognition of identity documents are regulated by national and international legal frameworks. Ensuring universal legal identity is critical for promoting inclusivity and reducing social and economic

inequality. However, there are still challenges in ensuring universal legal identity, such as the lack of birth registration and the accessibility of identity documents. The implications of legal identity on society are significant, and ongoing attention and regulation are necessary to ensure that all individuals have equal access to essential services and can exercise their rights.

The process of identification is the cornerstone of establishing legal identity. Identification involves the collection and verification of personal data to establish an individual's legal recognition. The collection of personal data may include biographical information, such as name, date of birth, and place of birth, as well as biometric data, such as fingerprints or facial recognition. (Alcock & Garvey, 2016). The verification process may involve comparing the collected data against a central database, such as a national registry, to establish the individual's identity. Once the individual's identity is established, they may be issued an identity document, such as a passport or a national ID card, which serves as proof of their legal identity (Lynch, M. 2018).

The process of identification is governed by national and international legal frameworks. National legal frameworks may differ from country to country, but they typically establish the requirements for identification and the issuance of identity documents (Malkin, 2018). International legal frameworks, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Convention on the Rights of the Child, recognize the importance of legal identity and establish standards for ensuring universal legal identity.

The process of identification has become more complex and sophisticated with the advancement of technology (Nissenbaum, 2010). Biometric identification, such as fingerprints or facial recognition, is increasingly being used as a means of establishing legal identity. However, there are concerns about the privacy and security implications of biometric identification, particularly when it is used by private companies or for surveillance purposes.

Ensuring universal legal identity requires addressing the challenges to the identification process. The lack of birth registration is a significant challenge, particularly in developing countries. According to the UNDP, around one-third of children worldwide are not registered at birth, which means they may be unable to access essential services or exercise their rights later in life (Zarsky, 2013). Other challenges include the cost and accessibility of identity documents, particularly for marginalized communities, and the lack of a harmonized legal framework for cross-border identification.

Mainly, the process of identification is crucial in establishing legal identity. It involves collecting and verifying personal data to establish an individual's legal recognition, and it is governed by national and international legal frameworks. The process of identification has become more complex with the advancement of technology, and it requires ongoing attention and regulation to ensure that it is used ethically and responsibly. Ensuring universal legal identity

requires addressing the challenges to the identification process, including the lack of birth registration and the cost and accessibility of identity documents.

Legal Frameworks Governing Legal Identity

Legal identity refers to the possession of an officially recognized and verifiable identity by an individual. Legal frameworks are crucial in ensuring that legal identity is acquired and maintained by all individuals. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) recognizes the right to legal identity as a fundamental human right, and several international legal instruments support this right. For instance, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights require states to ensure that all individuals enjoy the right to legal identity without discrimination (United Nations, 1966).

Challenges to Ensuring Universal Legal Identity

Despite the existence of legal frameworks, challenges exist in ensuring universal legal identity. These challenges include political instability, inadequate financial resources, lack of political will, and inadequate infrastructure. For instance, in developing countries, some individuals lack legal identity due to inadequate infrastructure to collect, verify and store identity data, and the inability to pay for identity registration services.

Implications of Legal Identity on Society

Legal identity has several implications for society. It promotes the protection of human rights, enhances social inclusion, and promotes the provision of essential services. Legal identity also enhances access to employment opportunities, financial services, and political participation, among others.

Universal Legal Identity and the Sustainable Development Goals

Universal legal identity is vital in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as it promotes social inclusion and provides access to essential services, such as healthcare, education, and financial services. SDG 16 aims to promote peaceful and inclusive societies, provide access to justice for all, and build effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels. Universal legal identity is an essential component of achieving SDG 16.

Legal Identity and Access to Essential Services

Legal identity promotes access to essential services, such as healthcare, education, and financial services. In developing countries, individuals without legal identity face difficulties accessing these services. For instance, without legal identity, an individual may be unable to open a bank account, access credit facilities, or receive government subsidies.

Legal Identity and the Exercise of Civil and Political Rights

Legal identity is essential in the exercise of civil and political rights. Without legal identity, individuals may be unable to participate in political processes, such as voting, and may face difficulties in accessing justice.

The Importance of Legal Identity and the Need for Ongoing Regulation

Legal identity is a fundamental human right that promotes social inclusion, access to essential services, and the exercise of civil and political rights. However, challenges exist in ensuring universal legal identity, and ongoing regulation is necessary to address these challenges. Legal frameworks and international legal instruments are crucial in promoting universal legal identity, and countries must ensure that they comply with these legal instruments.

Economic Identity

Economic identity refers to the various aspects of an individual or a group's economic life, including their occupation, income, consumption habits, financial behavior, and socioeconomic status. It is a multidimensional construct that influences an individual's well-being, social status, and sense of self. Economic identity has become increasingly important in recent years, as economic inequality and social mobility have become major concerns for policymakers and individuals alike.

One of the key aspects of economic identity is occupation. Occupation not only determines an individual's income and socioeconomic status but also plays a significant role in shaping their sense of self and social identity. As Schein (1978) notes, occupation is one of the primary sources of self-esteem and social status for individuals, as it provides a sense of purpose, social recognition, and a basis for self-evaluation.

Another important aspect of economic identity is consumption habits. People's consumption habits reflect their socioeconomic status, cultural background, and values, and can be a source of identity and social differentiation. For example, people may identify with particular brands or products as a way of expressing their social status or cultural identity.

Moreover, financial behavior is another key component of economic identity. Financial behavior refers to the ways in which individuals manage their finances, including their saving and spending habits, investment decisions, and attitudes towards risk. Research has shown that financial behavior is strongly influenced by an individual's socioeconomic background, cultural values, and life experiences (Hill, 2013).

In conclusion, economic identity is a multidimensional construct that encompasses various aspects of an individual or group's economic life, including their occupation, consumption habits,

and financial behavior. It is an essential aspect of people's sense of self and social identity and has significant implications for their well-being and social status.

Occupation and Economic Identity

Occupation and Economic Identity are intertwined, and one's occupation plays a crucial role in shaping their economic identity. Occupation provides a sense of purpose, social recognition, and a basis for self-evaluation, and influences an individual's income and socioeconomic status. Research has shown that occupation is one of the primary sources of self-esteem and social status for individuals (Schein, 1978). A person's job and career choices also affect their economic mobility and opportunities. Occupational mobility can significantly affect an individual's economic identity by increasing their income, improving their socioeconomic status, and providing them with a sense of personal achievement (Breen & Jonsson, 2005)

Occupation and Self-Esteem

Occupation has a significant impact on an individual's self-esteem, which is a critical component of economic identity. Research has shown that people often derive a sense of identity and self-worth from their occupation (Schein, 1978). Individuals who have occupations that are highly valued by society, such as doctors or lawyers, may have higher self-esteem than those in lower-status occupations. Conversely, those in lower-status occupations may experience a sense of shame or inferiority that can negatively impact their self-esteem. Thus, occupation can be an essential source of pride or insecurity for individuals, affecting their overall sense of self.

Occupation and Social Status

Occupation is also a significant determinant of an individual's social status. The prestige and social recognition associated with certain occupations can significantly influence an individual's economic identity. People in high-status occupations, such as doctors or lawyers, are often accorded greater respect and social recognition than those in lower-status occupations (Schein, 1978). Moreover, occupational status is often associated with educational attainment, income, and other markers of social status, further reinforcing the link between occupation and economic identity.

Occupational Mobility and Economic Identity

Occupational mobility is an important aspect of economic identity as it can significantly affect an individual's income, social status, and opportunities for personal achievement. Individuals who experience upward occupational mobility may see an improvement in their socioeconomic status and overall quality of life, while those who experience downward mobility may feel a sense of loss or diminished economic identity. Research has shown that occupational

mobility is influenced by a variety of factors, including educational attainment, social background, and labor market conditions (Breen & Jonsson, 2005).

Overall, occupation plays a critical role in shaping an individual's economic identity. It influences their self-esteem, social status, and opportunities for economic mobility. Understanding the interplay between occupation and economic identity can help policymakers develop more effective policies to address economic inequality and promote social mobility.

Implications of Economic Identity

These are significant, affecting people's well-being, social status, and opportunities for social mobility. Well-being and Economic Identity are closely related, with economic insecurity often leading to decreased well-being and negative impacts on mental health. Moreover, Economic Identity and Social Status are closely linked, with an individual's income and occupation often determining their social position and access to resources. Finally, Economic Identity and Social Mobility are critical aspects of economic inequality, with individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds often facing significant barriers to upward mobility (Breen & Jonsson, 2005). Understanding the implications of Economic Identity can inform policies aimed at reducing inequality and promoting social justice.

Economic insecurity, in particular, can have a significant impact on an individual's well-being. According to a study by Kahneman and Deaton (2010), people's emotional well-being is strongly correlated with their income up to a certain threshold, beyond which the relationship weakens. This suggests that economic security and a sense of financial stability are critical for people's mental and emotional health. Moreover, Economic Identity and Social Status are interrelated, with occupation and income often determining an individual's social position and access to resources (Erikson & John, 2010). Finally, Economic Identity and Social Mobility are critical for understanding economic inequality and the barriers that prevent people from achieving upward mobility (Corak, 2013). Human resource training and development can also contribute positively in economic security and a sense of financial stability (Asif, Khan, & Pasha, 2019).

Language learning involves not only the acquisition of a new means of communication, but also the acquisition of a new identity. As learners gain proficiency in a new language, they may also adopt new cultural norms, values, and beliefs, which can impact their sense of self. Moreover, language learning involves a complex psychological process that can affect an individual's self-perception and confidence. Learning a new language requires individuals to step out of their comfort zone, take risks, and tolerate ambiguity, which can be challenging and even intimidating.

The psychological process of language learning also involves the negotiation of identity. As learners develop new language skills, they may need to adjust their self-image and self-concept

to align with their new linguistic and cultural identity. This can be especially challenging for learners who feel a strong attachment to their native language and culture (Dey, 2021).

Furthermore, the psychological process of language learning can impact an individual's economic identity. Language proficiency can open up new job opportunities and increase earning potential, which can in turn shape an individual's economic identity. In conclusion, the psychological process of language learning is closely linked to the topic of "Identity as a Legal Concept & Economic Identity". Language learning involves the acquisition of a new cultural identity, negotiation of self-perception, and adjustment of economic identity.

Social Status and Economic Identity

These are closely intertwined, with an individual's income, occupation, and other markers of economic status playing a critical role in determining their social position and access to resources. Social status refers to the position an individual holds within a particular social hierarchy and the recognition and prestige accorded to that position (Dittmar, 2014). Economic Identity, on the other hand, refers to the various aspects of an individual's economic life, including their occupation, income, and consumption habits.

According to Dittmar (2014), social status and economic identity are closely linked, with people using their economic resources to signal their social status and identity. For example, individuals may use their income to purchase luxury goods as a way of signaling their high social status. Conversely, individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may experience a sense of stigma or shame associated with their economic position. This status and economic identity was badly affected by the recent pandemic (Asif, Pasha, Shafiq, & Craine, 2022).

Furthermore, social status and economic identity can also have implications for social mobility. Those from higher socioeconomic backgrounds are often more likely to have access to education and other resources that can promote upward mobility, while those from disadvantaged backgrounds may face significant barriers to social and economic advancement (Corak, 2013). Overall, understanding the interplay between social status and economic identity can help policymakers develop more effective policies to address economic inequality and promote social mobility.

Financial Behaviour and Life Experiences

Financial behavior is a critical component of economic identity, as it encompasses the ways in which individuals manage their finances, including their saving and spending habits, investment decisions, and attitudes towards risk. Financial behavior is shaped by a variety of factors, including an individual's socioeconomic background, cultural values, and life experiences.

Research has shown that life experiences can have a significant impact on an individual's financial behavior. Traumatic experiences, such as job loss or illness, can result in financial stress and insecurity, leading individuals to adopt more cautious financial behaviors (Hill, 2013). For example, individuals who have experienced financial hardship may be more likely to save money and avoid taking on debt.

Similarly, positive life experiences can also influence financial behavior. Individuals who have experienced financial success or stability may be more willing to take on risk and invest in the stock market or other ventures. Moreover, life experiences such as marriage, parenthood, or retirement can significantly affect financial behavior, as individuals adjust their spending and saving habits to meet changing circumstances (Hill, 2013).

Cultural values also play a critical role in shaping financial behavior. Research has shown that individuals from different cultural backgrounds may have different attitudes towards money and financial behavior (Furnham & Argyle, 1998). For example, some cultures place a higher value on saving and frugality, while others prioritize spending and consumerism. Moreover, cultural values can influence financial decision-making, such as whether to invest in the stock market or save money for a rainy day.

Socioeconomic background is another key factor that can influence financial behavior. Individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may be more likely to adopt more conservative financial behaviors, such as saving money and avoiding debt, while those from higher socioeconomic backgrounds may be more willing to take on risk and invest in the stock market (Hill, 2013). Moreover, individuals from disadvantaged backgrounds may have limited access to financial resources and education, which can further impact their financial behavior and opportunities for economic mobility.

Overall, financial behavior is shaped by a variety of factors, including an individual's life experiences, cultural values, and socioeconomic background. Understanding the interplay between these factors can help policymakers develop more effective policies to promote financial literacy, reduce economic inequality, and promote social mobility.

Conclusion

In conclusion, economic identity is a multidimensional construct that encompasses various aspects of an individual's economic life, including their occupation, consumption habits, financial behavior, and socioeconomic status. Occupation plays a crucial role in shaping economic identity by providing a sense of purpose, social recognition, and a basis for self-evaluation. Consumption habits and financial behavior are also essential components of economic identity and are influenced by an individual's socioeconomic background, cultural values, and life experiences.

Furthermore, economic identity has significant implications for an individual's well-being, social status, and opportunities for social mobility.

Understanding the interplay between these factors can inform policies aimed at promoting economic equality, social mobility, and financial literacy. For example, policies that address barriers to educational attainment and occupational mobility can help individuals achieve greater economic security and upward mobility. Policies that promote financial literacy and consumer protection can help individuals make more informed financial decisions and avoid financial exploitation. Moreover, policymakers can work to address structural inequalities and promote economic opportunities for marginalized communities, which can have a significant impact on economic identity and social mobility.

Economic identity is a critical aspect of people's sense of self and social identity, and policymakers and individuals alike should work to understand and address the various factors that shape it. By doing so, we can build a more just and equitable society that promotes economic well-being and social mobility for everyone.

References

- Alcock, A., & Michael, G., (2016). "Biometrics, Privacy and the Law." Biometrics and Government, edited by Elida S. Lagesen and Stig-Erik Baardsen, *Palgrave Macmillan*, 151-164.
- Asif, M., Pasha, M. A., Shafiq, S., & Craine, I. (2022). Economic Impacts of Post COVID-19. *Inverge Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(1), 56-65.
- Asif, M., Khan, A., & Pasha, M. A. (2019). Psychological capital of employees' engagement: moderating impact of conflict management in the financial sector of Pakistan. *Glob. Soc. Sci. Rev. IV*, 160-172.
- Breen, R., & Jonas O. J. (2005). "Inequality of Opportunity in Comparative Perspective: Recent Research on Educational Attainment and Social Mobility." *Annual Review of Sociology*, 31(1), 223-243.
- Corak, M. (2013) "Income Inequality, Equality of Opportunity, and Intergenerational Mobility." *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 27(3), 79-102.
- Department of Homeland Security. "Biometric Identification." *Department of Homeland Security*, 2018, <https://www.dhs.gov/biometric-identification>.
- Dey, M. (2021). Psychological processes in language learning and teaching: Scoping review and future research directions. *Journal of Psychological Perspective*, 3(2), 105-110.

- Dittmar, H. (2014). "The Social Psychology of Material Possessions: To Have Is to Be." *Annual Review of Psychology*, 64, 471-491.
- Erikson, R., & John, H. G. (2010). "Intergenerational Inequality: A Sociological Perspective." *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 24(3), 31-44.
- Hill, J. (2013). *Financial Behavior: Players, Services, Products, and Markets*. Routledge.
- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights." G.A. Res. 2200A (XXI), U.N. GAOR, 21st Sess., Supp. No. 16, U.N. Doc. A/6316 (1966).
- Kahneman, D., & Angus, D. (2010) "High Income Improves Evaluation of Life But Not Emotional Well-Being." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(38), 16489-16493.
- Lynch, M. (2018). *The Biometric State: The Promise and Peril of Digital Government in the New Age of Identity*. Cambridge University Press.
- Malkin, I. (2018) "The Birth Registration Crisis." *Harvard International Law Journal Online*, vol. 59.
- Nissenbaum, H. (2010) *Privacy in Context: Technology, Policy, and the Integrity of Social Life*. Stanford University Press.
- "Convention on the Rights of the Child." G.A. Res. 44/25, annex, 44 U.N. GAOR Supp. (No. 49) at 167, U.N. Doc. A/44/49 (1989). Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights.
- Schein, Edgar H. *Career Dynamics: Matching Individual and Organizational Needs*. Addison-Wesley, 1978.
- United Nations Development Programme. "Legal Identity for All: Why It Matters and What We Can Do About It." United Nations Development Programme, 2017, https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/democratic-governance/access_to_identity_andthe2030Agenda.html.
- United Nations General Assembly. "Universal Declaration of Human Rights." G.A. Res. 217A (III), U.N. Doc A/810, 1948.
- United Nations General Assembly. "International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination." G.A. Res. 2106 (XX), U.N. GAOR, 20th Sess., Supp. No. 14, U.N. Doc. A/6014, 1965.

United Nations General Assembly. "Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography." G.A. Res. 57/196, annex I, 57 U.N. GAOR Supp. (No. 49) at 299, U.N. Doc. A/57/49, 2002.

United Nations General Assembly. "Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development." A/RES/70/1, 2015.

United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees. "UNHCR Biometrics Identity Management." United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, 2014, <https://www.unhcr.org/54eb880f9.pdf>.

United States Government Accountability Office. "Identity Verification: IRS Can Improve Measures to Address Evolving Identity Theft Risks, but Additional Actions Are Needed." United States Government Accountability Office, 2019, <https://www.gao.gov/assets/700/696539.pdf>.

Zarsky, T. (2013). "The Trouble with Biometrics: The Growing Biometric Surveillance Society." *Harvard Civil Rights-Civil Liberties Law Review*, 48, 2013, 271-310. [Original source: <https://studycrumb.com/alphabetizer>]